

CAD Applications Of ANFIS Model For Annular Ring MPA

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Abstract-A novel annular ring Microstrip patch antenna (ARMPA) with circularly polarized (CP) operation is proposed and a soft computing technique i.e. ANFIS model is prepared for CAD and other microwave applications. Soft computing techniques do not require complex calculations and is very fast. For training and testing of model a commercially available ANSOFT HFSS v.13 is used to extract the 108 data sets of ARMPA having different sensitive parameters related to antenna dimensions and substrate materials. Apart from 108 simulated data sets, 96 were used for training and remaining 12 were utilized for testing of trained ANFIS model. The average percentage errors (APE) are calculated regarding performance of training and testing of ANFIS model. The APE of model found in testing for resonant frequency of proposed ARMPA is 0.1634. The very low error indicates that the models can be successfully applied for optimization of physical parameter of ARMPA for computer aided design (CAD) applications. Thus the proposed trained ANFIS model can be used efficiently to evaluation of resonant frequency for wireless communication where wide-band and compact CP is required any time instead of running HFSS simulation software or other complex mathematical procedure.

Keywords-Annular Ring, Microstrip Patch Antenna, Circular Polarization, Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS), Training & Testing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Microstrip patch antennas (MPAs) are used mostly because of their effortless, conformability, low industrialized cost, light credence, low profile, reproducibility, reliability, and ease in production [1-10]. These features have improved the applications of MPAs. MPAs have been used in various shapes such as rectangular, circular, triangular, elliptical, trapezoidal, annular ring and many more. Annular ring MPA are easy in design and can be used as an echoing antenna. In past, the analysis of MPA is normally done by the cavity model [7], and transmission line model [8]. But these techniques can't be used in irregular or complex shapes of MPAs. So for irregular or complex shapes antennas, other techniques such as FDTD [9] and MoM [10] were applied. These techniques were very

complicated and highly time consuming. So, now days another techniques i.e. simulation as IE3D, HFSS, CST studio etc. [11-12] are used for analysis of complex shaped MPA. Yet again these analysis techniques were also very much time consuming because it is based on head and trial basis. Soft computing techniques such as artificial neural network (ANN) [13], ANFIS [14-15] and support vector machine (SVM) [16] eradicate the complex mathematical procedures and time consuming processes of MPA design. These models have been widely used for analysis and synthesis of hodgepodge of MPAs in the literature [17-29]. In these literatures analysis and synthesis were carried out to determine some performance parameters and design the model of MPAs having various shapes with soft computing techniques such as ANN, ANFIS and SVM. Hence, ability and flexibility to learn, less information requirement, fast real-time operation, and ease of accomplishment features have made these techniques popular among researchers in the last few years.

In this paper ANFIS is used for analysis and synthesis of proposed ARMPA, because ANFIS is an universal estimator [14]. It constructs complex and nonlinear relationship between set of inputs and outputs data. It combines the advantages of the fuzzy inference system (FIS) and learning capability of ANN in a single model [15]. The proposed ARMPA structure is taken as base paper [11] published in MOTL journal by Ajay kumar e.t.al. The proposed antenna is used in the application of wireless communication of 2GHz to 6 GHz where very compact and circular polarization is required. For designing of ANFIS model of proposed ARMPA, 108 ARMPAs having various sensitive dimensions were simulated by commercially available ANSOFT HFSS v.13 software. Apart from 108 data sets 96 of data sets were utilized for training purpose and remaining 12 of data sets were used for testing of trained model. The functional block diagram of ANN/ANFIS model is given in fig.1. The validation of this ANFIS models were also tested and verified by simulation and measured results.

Fig.1 The functional block diagram of ANFIS model

ARMPA Geometry and ANFIS Modeling

The rudimentary geometry of ARMPA is shown in fig.2. It consists of a pair of slit and rectangular ground shaped patches of $4 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$. The deformed bent feeding is used in this MPA and also shown in fig. 2. In order to determine the value of resonant frequency of ARMPA for ANFIS model, the recreation is performed by ANSOFT HFSS v.13. The 108 ARMPAs having various sets of sensitive parameter of antenna dimensions and substrate

material collected by HFSS simulation are listed in table 1. The most sensitive parameters, which affect the results of ARMPA, are selected for the parametric study. They are truncated length (ΔL), patch length (d), slit length (ΔL_s), feed width (W_f), relative permittivity of substrate material (ϵ_r) and thickness (h). The left over parameters did not show momentous effect on the impedance bandwidth, and were kept invariant throughout. To precisely understand the sway of these parameters on its impedance bandwidth, only one parameter at a time was varied, whereas others were kept constant. These ARMPA sets of MPA operate in resonant frequency range of 2.0-6.0 GHz for application of wireless communication in CP operation.

Table 1: 108 Parametric sets for simulation of ARMPAs.

Number of Simulation Sets	Sensitive parameters					
	ΔL (mm)	ΔL_s (mm)	d (mm)	W_f (mm)	h (mm)	ϵ_r
36	5.6, 5.7,	9.0, 9.5, 10.5	3.5	1.3, 1.5	0.8	2.2, 2.33
36	5.5, 5.6,	9.0, 9.5, 10.0	4.0	1.5, 1.7	1.6	2.33, 4.4
36	5.5, 5.7,	9.0, 10, 10.5	4.5	1.3, 1.7	3.2	2.2, 4.4

Fig. 2 Elemental Geometry of the proposed ARMPA (a) Microstrip patch and (b) feeding line.

These sensitive parameter sets of simulated ARMPAs were given as an input and their particular resonant frequency values of HFSS were given as output for training of ANFIS. The 96 simulated data sets arbitrarily use for training process. The basic construction for the training of ANFIS is given in fig. 3.

Fig.3 Basic construction for training of ANFIS model.

In proposed article the basic parameters of ANFIS model is configure on trial basis by training process. After many trials in training, the best set-up of parameter is found for ANFIS model and given in table 2. The final network architecture of trained model of proposed MPA, the ANFIS model is given in fig. 4. Now the model is ready for testing. The left over 12 simulated inputs data sets now utilized for testing of trained model. The tested results for 12 data sets and simulated results of HFSS v.13 are shown in table 3. The APE of ANFIS model for tested results are then calculated for these 12 data sets and also shown in table 3. The formula for calculation of APE is given in equation 1. Finally simulated and ANFIS results are compared and found in very good agreement.

$$APE = \frac{\sum |f_{HFSS} - f_{ANFIS}|}{number_of_antenna} \times 100$$

(1)

Table 2: Fitting parameter of ANFIS model

Parameters	Type
ANFIS model	Sugeno type
Input/output Membership Function (MF)	Gaussian/Linear
Number of Membership Function	42
Number of fuzzy rules	42
Training epochs	128
Number of Inputs	6
Number of nonlinear Parameter	6*42*1=252

Table 3: The comparative results of HFSS simulation and ANFIS model

Test patches	Input dimensions (mm)						Results (GHz)		
	ΔL	ΔL_s	d	W_f	h	ϵ_r	HFSS simulation	ANFIS	
							R_f	R_f	
1	5.6	9.0	3.5	1.3	0.8	2.2	3.752	3.741	
2	5.6	9.5	3.5	1.5	0.8	2.33	3.881	3.874	
3	5.7	9.0	3.5	1.5	0.8	2.2	3.801	3.807	
4	5.8	9.5	3.5	1.3	0.8	2.33	3.985	3.983	
5	5.6	10	4.0	1.5	0.8	2.2	4.088	4.076	
6	5.5	9.0	4.0	1.7	1.6	2.33	3.947	3.942	
7	5.6	10	4.0	1.7	1.6	2.33	4.051	4.042	
8	5.7	10.5	4.0	1.5	1.6	4.4	4.023	4.033	
9	5.7	9.5	4.0	1.5	1.6	4.4	3.912	3.903	
10	5.5	10	4.5	1.3	3.2	4.4	4.110	4.097	
11	5.8	10.5	4.5	1.7	3.2	2.2	3.783	3.763	
12	5.8	9.0	4.5	1.7	3.2	4.4	3.853	3.865	
Average Percentage Error (APE)								0.1634	

Fig. 4 ANFIS model for ARMPA.

II. RESULT, CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

In proposed paper ANFIS model was anticipated to analyze the resonant frequency of ARMPAs. The results obtained by HFSS simulation and ANFIS model for 12 tested sets of ARMPA for various sensitive parameters are listed in table 3. In table 3, it can be seen that the tested results by trained ANFIS model are in very good agreement with simulated results. The APE of ANFIS model results for resonant frequency is found 0.1634. The very close results and fewer APEs point out its validation. Here, it is required to clarify that; the better outcome may be obtained by choosing other sets of data from the ones which is uses in this proposed MPA, or by collecting more sets of data values for training. Major benefits of the ANFIS model is that, after once the model is ready, there is no requirement of any training again for each new calculation. The model is not limited for the resonant frequency analysis, but it can be useful for other parameters of similar MPA. It takes in fraction of seconds in envisaging the required result after doing training properly. The approach has created more accurate result; hence the model is very helpful for microwave integrated circuits design and CAD applications.

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